

Covid 19 Pandemic Impact on Social Relations

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Abstract:- COVID 19 crisis has been one of the most testing and trying non- military catastrophes that mankind is facing. It has crossed the boundaries of nations, class, creed, religion and economy thus affecting every single human being on the earth. The research is still on to gauge and judge the impact of COVID19 Pandemic crisis on different dimensions related to humans. Impact on social relations is one such area that needs a de- novo look to ascertain the change in the fabric of the society that this pandemic has brought.

Keywords:- COVID 19 Pandemic, Impact on Social relations, Awareness about COVID, Effect on daily life due to COVID, Changes in society due to COVID, Measures to deal with COVID,

I. INTRODUCTION

COVID 19 Pandemic came as a sudden wave of disaster and destruction for the entire world. It engulfed the entire human race into its clutches within a very short span of time. Due to better connectivity by land, rail, water and air the spread of the virus was exponential. Apart from having total collapse of economy, unemployment rise and shutting down of business entities, what has been most severely hit and has created a dent is the Social relations and the basic fiber of the society.

An unprecedented fall of care and concern was noticed all across the globe cutting across caste, creed, religion and nations. Very disturbing reports in media and social media about stranded parents, left alone children, abandoned family members were more of a norm than an exception. But at the end of it, all was not that bad, we as a society especially in India stood up to the occasion and faced the pandemic head on, together with our near and dear ones.

The need for a cohesive and caring family has been brought to light with more prominence by this pandemic.

A. Effect of COVID19 Crisis for India In Particular & World In General.

By the end of 2019, the world has started to feel the initial effects of the Corona virus. What was initially being thought as a localized and isolated case of virus infection did actually spread to most of the continents by March 2021. This was followed by unprecedented lockdowns and curtailing of basic human rights by Governments across the globe. Some of the steps taken by countries to check the spread of virus were:-

- Strict control on movement of citizens.
- Almost complete ban on private transport.

- Discontinuation of international and domestic flights and sea movements.
- Making mask mandatory for all.
- Social distancing norm strictly enforced.
- Focus of personal and societal hygiene and sanitation.
- Shutdown of educational institutions and following online mode of teaching.
- Work from home became more of an accepted norm.
- Mass layoffs by business enterprises.
- In India, villages saw mass influx of population from towns and cities.
- In India, Joint family system was in a way revived with families staying at one place to cut down on expenditure.
- In India, small scale industries and agriculture related activities got a new lease of life.
- Societies initially were very skeptical and unsure about how to respond to this unseen, life threatening pandemic. In the beginning not so happy and healthy tales of human reaction and family relations were the TRP gainers on social media platforms. But as the time progressed and people got adapted to the pandemic and its effects, there was a marked shift noticed in care and compassion among families and societies.

B. Find out the impact of COVID19 on humans and their lives.

COVID 19 had and is having a very visible and prominent impact on humans and their lives. We can see the changes in the living, working, travelling, attending social gatherings and even funereal proceedings post COVID 19 pandemic.

The noteworthy impact of the pandemic on humans and their lives can be summarized as follows:-

- People initially became scared and were self centered.
- Family ties and relations were the worst affected, news of abandoned patients, unclaimed bodies and people being denied entry into their own house, town or villages were reported in the beginning, however with passage of time the situation improved.
- Hoarding and black marketing of food and drugs were reported all across the society.
- Medical facilities and services were stretched to the brim. With complete failure of primary and secondary medical care and support the burden and load came upon tertiary and specialist medical care facilities.
- Shortage of medicines, drugs and oxygen support system created a panic like situation in the society.

- Due to loss of jobs by people many families had to dig upon their savings and look for alternate support mechanism.

C. Survey for impact on social relations.

An in-depth survey was conducted in Dehradun as part of the project to find the impact of COVID19 crisis on social relations in general and in specific to the residents of Dehradun. The participants of the survey were relatives, neighbours, friends, peers and random persons who were willing to be part of this survey.

The participants of the survey were asked questions to assess their personal views on the COVID19 pandemic and its effect on social relations that they faced or encountered.

The questions posed to them were:-

- 1) What do they understand with the term COVID19 and what in their views are the reasons for its occurrence?
- 2) How has Corona affected them in their daily life and what changes it has forced in their daily routine?

- What do they understand with the term COVID19 and what in their views are the reasons for its occurrence?

- 3) What have been the biggest changes in their immediate family, friends and relative's attitude and conduct due to Corona?
- 4) How has the society around them changed due to Covid?
- 5) When have they realised that Covid changes have started affecting their social relations?
- 6) Have the older generation accepted the social changes gracefully?
- 7) Did children show any signs of abnormality due to changes brought by Covid restrictions?
- 8) Are there any positive spinoffs of COVID19 crisis?
- 9) finally, overall are they happy or unhappy or neutral?

The target group was a wide cross section of society and comprised of responding able age group from 12 years to 80 years male and female both.

The reply to the questionnaire has been summarised as under:-

II. AWARENESS ABOUT COVID 19 IN SOCIETY

- How has Corona affected them in their daily life and what changes it has forced in their daily routine?

III. COVID 19 EFFECT IN DAY TO DAY LIFE OF SOCIETY

- What have been the biggest changes in their immediate family, friends and relatives attitude and conduct due to Corona?

IV. CHANGES IN SOCIETY DUE TO COVID 19

• How has the society around them changed due to Covid?

V. EXTENT OF CHANGE IN SOCIETY DUE TO COVID 19

• When have they realised that Covid changes have started affecting their social relations?

VI. REALISATION OF CHANGE IN SOCIAL RELATIONS

- Have the older generation accepted the social changes gracefully?

VII. CHANGE ACCEPTANCE BY SENIOR GENERATION

- Did children show any signs of abnormality due to changes brought by Covid restrictions?

VII. SIGNS OF CHANGE IN CHILDREN DUE TO COVID 19

- Are there any positive spinoffs of COVID19 crisis?

IX. MAJOR CHANGES IN SOCIETY DUE TO COVID 19

- finally, overall are they happy or unhappy or neutral?

X. FINAL MENTAL STATUS OF SOCIETY DUE TO COVID 19

- Measures to Deal with the COVID19 Pandemic
 - India as a nation has handled COVID19 crisis pretty well keeping in mind the vast population and expanse of our country. However still there is a dire need to educate people in preventive care for reduction of COVID cases. The enlightenment has to come from within and not as a result of fear or compulsion.
 - Education of the children is getting adversely affected, long term planning for mode and conduct of classes and exams have to be defined by the competent authority.
 - Unemployment has increased and economy is all time low, self help groups, village level cluster economy and regional development has to be made the new mantra.
 - Social media and online or offline news platforms have to be more responsible and answerable.
 - Guidelines for COVID19 are to be followed by all concerned.
 - Truthful and responsible media reporting are a must for print and electronic media.
 - TRP competition between channels has given rise to unhealthy practice of race for time on air rather than content quality. Governing body has to take a note of it and be more proactive and assertive.
 - Psychologically the COVID19 crisis has taken a big toll on everyone. Mentoring and counselling at schools, workplace, by aanganbadi workers and NGOs etc has to be made compulsory.
 - Hospital staff, sanitary work force, Security agencies and all other people and organisations dealing with COVID have to be given due recognition and support.

XI. CONCLUSION

COVID19 crisis and such like catastrophic situations are bound to happen in future also. With the **World as a village** concept we are all connected in real time and no one is isolated. The need therefore is to have a common understanding, mutual responsibility and integrated approach to deal with such like situations by one and all.

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